

Assessments of plant indicator and invasive species in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists

Guideline and Protocols

Version 1.1

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Chapter 1: Background

Monitoring Ecosystem Services (ES) provided by wetlands is crucial for assessing the state of the wetlands, their changes over time, and the impacts of conservation and restoration measures. The engagement of non-experts as Citizen Scientists can support this ES monitoring by delivering large amounts of data otherwise not (easily) available. Additionally, Citizen Science helps raise awareness among local people about the significance of wetlands for human well-being, thereby enhancing citizens' stewardship.

In the Horizon Europe Project **RESTORE4LIFE**, 101112736 (<https://restore4life.eu/>), we have created a **toolbox for monitoring ES of wetlands** (Deliverable D3.5), covering both geospatial and on-the-ground methods (publicly available from Dec 2025 on our webpage and Zenodo). One focus was on developing Citizen Science protocols for on-the-ground measurements that provide reliable and valuable data for wetland assessments. Various Citizen Scientists helped us test the developed protocols regarding their intelligibility, user-friendliness, and applicability before release. To assess the quality and explanatory power of the data collected by Citizen Scientists, we compared them with data collected by scientists using more advanced methods. The results of these quality checks can be found in our toolbox D3.5.

The following topics were covered and published separately: (1) water body quality, (2) organic carbon storage in tree biomass and wetland soils, (3) plant diversity, and (4) recreational and educational services. Each published document consists of several parts: Citizen Scientists' protocol(s) for assessing data in the field; Citizen Scientists' protocol(s) for indoor analyses (if applicable); Citizen Scientists' protocol(s) for calculations (if applicable); and a guideline for scientists on further data processing.

The current document addresses the identification of plant indicator and invasive species to determine plant diversity and status in wetlands.

Chapter 2: Herbaceous plants in wetlands

Surveying herbaceous plant species provides valuable insights into the ecological conditions and health of habitats such as meadows, floodplains or peatlands. Different species have specific environmental preferences, so their presence and abundance reflect factors like soil nutrients, moisture, acidity, and light availability – all of which also affect carbon storage and ecosystem function.

Citizen Science helps document the most common species along a transect by estimating their abundance using the Fisher scale. Identifying plants with the Flora Incognita app and photographing key features (whole plant, leaf, flower) ensures reliable species records and helps distinguish native from non-native plants. Equally, Citizen Scientists can record the occurrence of invasive plant species.

Adding **indicator values** (based on Latin species names) offers further ecological interpretation. These values describe each plant's typical environmental requirements, such as moisture, nitrogen or pH, and support a deeper understanding of habitat quality and possible changes due to climate change or land use. Flora incognita offers these values for each species under "traits".

You could also use the Ellenberg indicator values. Add the plant's Latin name to <https://statedv.boku.ac.at/zeigerwerte/>. Unfortunately, this platform is only available in German. Thus, we have added an English translation on the following pages.

ELLENBERG'S INDICATOR VALUES

Light number (L)		
<i>Value</i>	<i>designation</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
1	Deep shade plant	still less than 1%, rarely occurring at more than 30% r. B.
2	Deep shade to shade plant	standing between 1 and 3
3	Shade plant	mostly at less than 5% r. B., but also in brighter areas
4	Shade to partial shade plant	standing between 3 and 5
5	Partial shade plant	only exceptionally in full light, but mostly at more than 10% r. B.
6	Partial shade to half light plant	between 5 and 7, rarely less than 20% r. B.
7	Halblichtpflanze	mostly in full light, but also in the shade up to about 30% r. B.
8	Half light to full light plant	Light plant, only exceptionally at less than 40% r. B.
9	Full light plant	only in fully irradiated outdoor locations, not less than 50% r. B.

Temperature number (T)		
<i>Value</i>	<i>designation</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
1	Cold indicator	only in high mountain areas, i.e. the alpine and nival levels
2	Cold to cool indicator	between 1 and 3 standing (many alpine species)
3	Cooling indicator	mainly in subalpine areas
4	Cool to moderate heat indicator	between 3 and 5 standing (especially high montane and montane species)
5	Moderate heat indicator	occurring in low to montane areas (mainly in submontane temperate areas)
6	Moderate to warm indicator	between 5 and 7 standing (planar to collin)
7	Heat indicator	in northern Central Europe only in relatively warm lowlands
8	Heat to extreme heat indicators	standing between 7 and 9 (mostly with sub-Mediterranean heavyweight)
9	extreme heat indicator	Mediterranean (in Central Europe only in the warmest places, e.g. in the Upper Rhine region)

Humidity number (F)		
<i>Value</i>	<i>designation</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
1	Severe drought zeiger	limited to dry soils, viable in often drying places
2	Severe dryness to dryness indicator	standing between 1 and 3
3	Drying indicator	more common on dry soils than on fresh ones, absent on moist ones
4	Dryness to freshness indicator	standing between 3 and 5
5	Freshness indicator	Focus on medium-moist soils
6	Freshness to humidity indicator	standing between 5 and 7
7	Humidity indicator	Emphasis on well-moistened but not wet soils
8	Humidity to wetness indicator	standing between 7 and 9
9	Wetness indicator	Focus on often wet (air-poor) soils
10	Alternating water indicator	Aquatic plant that can survive for a long time without water covering the soil
11	Aquatic plant	Rooted under water, but at least temporarily rising above the surface or floating plant
12	Underwater plant	(almost) constantly submerged
~	Pointer for strong change	<i>additional information</i>
=	Flood indicator	<i>additional information</i>

Reaction number (R)		
<i>Value</i>	<i>designation</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
1	Strong acid indicator	only occurs on acidic, never on slightly acidic to alkaline soils
2	Strong acid to acid indicator	standing between 1 and 3
3	Acid indicator	Emphasis on acidic soils, only exceptionally in the neutral range
4	Acid to moderate acid indicator	standing between 3 and 5
5	Moderate acid indicator	rarely found on strongly acidic and neutral to alkaline soils
6	Moderate acid to weak acid/weak base indicator	standing between 5 and 7
7	Weak acid to weak base indicator	never on strongly acidic soils
8	Weak acid/weak base to base and lime indicators	between 7 and 9, i.e. mostly pointing to limestone
9	Base and calcium indicators	always on calcareous soils

Nitrogen number (N)		
<i>Value</i>	<i>designation</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
1	Extreme nitrogen deficiency indicator	indicating the poorest nitrogen locations
2	Extreme nitrogen to nitrogen deficiency indicator	standing between 1 and 3
3	Nitrogen deficiency indicator	on N-poor sites more frequently than on medium-poor sites, only exceptionally on N-rich sites
4	Nitrogen deficiency to moderate nitrogen indicator	standing between 3 and 5
5	Moderate nitrogen indicator	indicating moderately N-rich sites, less frequently on N-poor and N-rich
6	Moderate nitrogen to nitrogen rich indicator	standing between 5 and 7
7	Nitrogen abundance indicator	more frequently on N-rich sites than on mediocre sites, only exceptionally on N-poor sites
8	pronounced nitrogen indicator	standing between 7 and 9
9	excessive nitrogen indicator	concentrated in excessively N-rich locations (livestock plant, pollution indicator)

REFERENCES

ELLENBERG, H., WEBER, H.E., DÜLL, R., WIRTH, V., WEBER, P., WERNER, D.: "Zeigerwerte von Pflanzen in Mitteleuropa", Scripta Geobotanica 18 (2.Auflage 1992).

Chapter 3: Identifying plants

3.1. OUTDOOR PROTOCOL

MATERIALS:

- ❖ 10-20 m measuring tape or rope

TASKS:

1. At each site, select a section 10-20 meters along the path and mark the ends with a ribbon. Take a photo of the site.
3. Walk along the path and determine the five to seven most common non-woody species on both sides up to 2 m from the path. Estimate the abundances of these five species using the Fischer scale (shown below).

Abundances according to the Fischer scale (1986):

Symbol	Abundance	Areal coverage
1	Rare, 1-2 plants per species	< 5%
2	2- 10 plants per species	< 10 %
3	Common, >10 plants per species	<20 %
4	Very common	20 - 50 %
5	Dominating	50 - 100 %

4. Identify each species using the "Flora Incognita" App. Take a picture of the entire plant, the leaf, and the flower (if present). Check the identification by comparing it to the plant description in the app.
5. Then, look under "traits". Here you find information on the species' distribution, protection status, and habitat preferences.

Note whether the species is **native or not** (neophyte).

Note the numbers of the **indicator values** Nutrients, Moisture, Light, Temperature, and Soil Reaction (pH). These indicators describe the plant's habitat preferences. The higher the number, the more light, soil moisture, nutrients, temperature, and pH the plant prefers or tolerates.

We appreciate your support!

Your data provide information on the wetland vegetation, plant diversity, and the health of the ecosystem.

This helps to develop management strategies to restore and protect the wetland.

DATA SHEET

Name/ID of Citizen Scientist:	
Date:	Time:
GPS data of site:	Weather:

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FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE